

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Response of off-season strawberries (*Fragaria sp.*) production under the effects of paclobutrazol and drought stress

Komang Sandiasa, I Nyoman Rai *, Ida Ayu Putri Darmawati and I Gusti Ngurah Santosa

Laboratory of Agronomy and Horticulture, Faculty of Agriculture, Gedung Agrokomples Lt.2 Kampus PB. Sudirman, Denpasar-Bali, Indonesia.

GSC Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 2024, 26(01), 025–032

Publication history: Received on 26 September 2023; revised on 19 November 2023; accepted on 22 November 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/gscbps.2024.26.1.0471>

Abstract

Strawberry (*Fragaria sp.*) is a fruit crop harvested seasonally with the peak season from August to November while the off-season harvest is January to June with limited harvest. The purpose of this study was to find the concentration of paclobutrazol and the level of drought stress for off-season strawberry production. This research conducted on April to July 2023. The experiment used a factorial Randomized Block Design consisting of 2 factors and 3 replications with 16 treatment combinations. The first factor was paclobutrazol consisting of four levels, namely P_0 = control, P_1 = 10,000 ppm, P_2 = 20,000 ppm and P_3 = 30,000 ppm and the second factor was the level of drought stress consisting of four levels i.e. C_0 = 100% field capacity, C_1 = 80% field capacity, C_2 = 60% field capacity and C_3 = 40% field capacity. The results showed that paclobutrazol accelerated flowering time, increased fruit set, leaf relative water content, root length, chlorophyll content, but decreased the number of fruits formed, harvested fruits, fruit diameter, harvested fruit weight, weight per fruit, root oven dry weight, percentage of fallen fruits and total soluble solids. Drought stress level increased leaf relative water content, root length, root oven dry weight, percentage of fallen fruit, percentage of fruit set, but decreased number of flowers formed, fruits harvested, weight of fruits harvested, weight per fruit, fruit diameter, total soluble solids, chlorophyll content and delayed flowering time.

Keywords: Drought stress; Off-season; Paclobutrazol; Strawberry

1. Introduction

Strawberry (*Fragaria sp.*) is one of the important horticultural commodities in the world, especially for countries that have a tropical climate. Strawberries are a type of annual plant where strawberries can live up to two years. Based on Bali central statistics agency data [1] shows that the national production of strawberries reached 98,596 tons. Indonesia has the potential to develop strawberry plants for consumption as fresh fruit or processed fruit. Pancasari Village is one of the strawberry producing villages in Bali Province. In the period of January to June strawberry production has decreased due to high rainfall. To support production during the off-season can be done by modifying the growing environment, namely providing the application of growth regulators and drought stress.

One of the growth regulators that can be used to shift vegetative growth towards generative growth is paclobutrazol. Paclobutrazol is able to increase the average peach fruit weight up to 49% [2], increase the weight and percentage of total pear yield [3], increase the yield and number of apple fruits [4]. Meanwhile Rumada et al. [5] reported paclobutrazol is able to accelerate the time to start appearing flowers on mangosteen plants.

Apart from the application of paclobutrazol, drought stress can be used to increase crop production. Rahayu et al. [6] reported that the duration of drought stress given for 2 weeks accelerated the flowering time in Madura tangerine

* Corresponding author: I Nyoman Rai

plants. Research result Roosa et al. [7] reported that soil moisture content of 75% field capacity produced higher plant height, number of stolons and chlorophyll content in strawberry plants.

2. Material and methods

The research was conducted from April to July 2023 in a strawberry farm owned by a farmer in Pancasari Village, Sukasada Subdistrict, Buleleng Regency with coordinates 8°14'42.3 "S 115°09'03.1 "E located in the highlands at an altitude of 1,300 m above sea level (asl). Observations were conducted in the field and Agronomy and Horticulture Laboratory, Faculty of Agriculture, Udayana University. The study used 5.5-month-old strawberry plants. The plants have been fruiting and producing. The materials used include paclobutrazol, manure, KNO₃ fertilizer and compound NPK fertilizer. The tools used include tools for paclobutrazol application, chlorophyll meter SPAD (Soil Plant Analysis Development) 502, petri dish, oven, 60watt bohlamp, caliper, hand counter, analytical balance, and °Brix Refractometer 0-32%.

The study used a factorial randomized group design with two factors. The first factor was paclobutrazol concentration with four levels: 0 ppm (P₀), 10,000 ppm (P₁), 20,000 ppm (P₂) and 30,000 ppm (P₃). The second factor is drought stress with four levels: 100% field capacity (C₀), 80% field capacity (C₁), 60% field capacity (C₂) and 40% field capacity (C₃). Thus, 16 treatment combinations were repeated 3 times so that there were 48 experimental units.

Variables observed included: height per plant, flowering time, relative water content of leaves, chlorophyll content of leaves, root length, root oven dry weight, number of flowers formed, number of fruits formed, percentage of fruit set, number of harvested fruits per plant, percentage of fallen fruits, weight of harvested fruits per plant, average weight per fruit, total soluble solids and fruit diameter. Then observation data were analyzed using Analysis of variance (Anova). Single factors were further tested using the least significant difference (LSD) test at the 5% level.

3. Results

3.1. Plant height

The treatment of paclobutrazol had a very significant effect on plant height. In the P₂ treatment, the plant height was the lowest compared to the control. Drought stress treatment had no significant effect on plant height but there was a tendency in the C₃ treatment to be lower than the control presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Effect of paclobutrazol treatment and drought stress on plant height (cm), leaf chlorophyll content (SPAD), leaf relative water content (%) and root length (cm)

Treatment	Plant height (cm)			Leaf chlorophyll content (SPAD)			Relative water content of leaves (%)			Root length (cm)		
Concentration of paclobutrazol (ppm)												
P ₀	12.33	(3.13)	a	35.62	(5.22)	c	35.27	(5.17)	bc	26.59	(4.52)	a
P ₁	6.39	(2.31)	bc	36.23	(5.26)	b	34.27	(5.06)	d	27.13	(4.56)	a
P ₂	6.18	(2.28)	d	36.88	(5.31)	a	41.59	(5.54)	a	27.01	(4.54)	a
P ₃	6.28	(2.30)	cd	36.63	(5.29)	ab	35.11	(5.17)	cd	27.30	(4.58)	a
LSD 5%	0.10			0.03			0.25			0.10		
Drought stress (%)												
C ₀	10.76	(2.54)	a	36.61	(5.29)	a	37.51	(5.33)	a	25.44	(4.43)	c
C ₁	10.27	(2.49)	a	36.39	(5.28)	a	36.50	(5.25)	a	26.39	(4.49)	bc
C ₂	10.41	(2.51)	a	36.36	(5.27)	ab	38.17	(5.28)	a	28.46	(4.67)	a
C ₃	10.14	(2.48)	a	35.98	(5.25)	b	34.37	(5.08)	b	27.74	(4.62)	a
LSD 5%	0.10			0.03			0.25			0.10		

Description: Numbers followed by the same letter in the same treatment and column show no significant difference in the 5% level of the least significant difference test (LSD). The numbers in parentheses are the result of data transformation. While the numbers that are not in parentheses are the original data.

3.2. Leaf chlorophyll content (SPAD)

Paclobutrazol treatment significantly increased leaf chlorophyll content. The highest leaf chlorophyll content was obtained in P₂ at 36.88 SPAD but not significantly different from P₁ (36.23 SPAD) and P₃ (36.53 SPAD). The smallest leaf chlorophyll content obtained in P₀ (35.62 SPAD) was significantly different from P₁, P₂, P₃. In the drought stress treatment, the highest leaf chlorophyll content was obtained in C₀ (36.62 SPAD) and was not significantly different from C₁ and C₂ (36.39 SPAD) and (36.36 SPAD) respectively but significantly different from C₃ (35.98 SPAD) presented in Table 1.

3.3. Leaf relative water content (%)

In paclobutrazol treatment, the highest leaf relative water content was obtained in P₂ which was 41.59% significantly different from other treatments. The lowest leaf relative water content was obtained in P₁ 34.27%. In the drought stress treatment, the relative water content of leaves was not significantly different in all treatments. However, there is a tendency that the highest leaf relative water content in C₂ is 38.17% and the lowest is obtained in C₃ (34.37%) presented in Table 1.

3.4. Root length

Root length in the treatment of paclobutrazol concentration was not significantly different in all treatments, but there was a tendency for the longest roots in P₃ which was 27.30 cm higher than P₀ by 2.60%. In the drought stress treatment, the longest root length obtained in C₂ was not significantly different from C₁ and C₃ with each root length of 28.46 cm, 26.39 cm and 27.74 cm but significantly different from C₀ (25.44 cm) presented in Table 1.

3.5. Time to flowering (DAT)

In the treatment of paclobutrazol concentration, the fastest flowering time was obtained in P₂, which was 7.50 days after treatment (DAT), significantly different from the treatment of P₀, P₁, and P₃ with flowering time of 17.44 DAT, 17.63 DAT and 17.44 DAT, respectively. In terms of treatment P₂ is faster flowering compared to P₁ which is 57.45%. In the treatment of drought stress, all treatments had no significant effect on flowering time, but there was a tendency for faster flowering time at C₂ 13.63 DAT presented in Table 2.

3.6. Number of flowers formed (florets)

The highest number of flowers formed in paclobutrazol treatment was obtained in P₀ (8.00 florets) and significantly different from P₁ (5.00 florets), P₂ (6.00 florets) and P₃ (7.00 florets). In this case the number of flowers formed in P₀ is more than P₁ by 37.5%. In the drought stress treatment, the highest number of flowers formed was obtained in C₀ which was 7.00 flowers and significantly different from all treatments C₁, C₂ and C₃ which were each 6.00 flowers presented in Table 2.

3.7. Number of fruits formed

In the treatment of paclobutrazol, the highest number of fruits formed was obtained in the control treatment (6.00 fruits), significantly different from the treatments P₁ (4.00 fruits), P₂ (4.00 fruits) and P₃ (5.00 fruits). This shows that the number of fruits formed in P₀ is higher than P₁ and P₂ by 33.33%. While in the drought stress treatment, the number of fruits formed was highest in C₀ (6.00 fruits) and not significantly different in C₃ (6.00) but significantly different in C₁ (4.00) and C₂ (4.00) presented in Table 2.

3.8. Number of harvest fruits

In the paclobutrazol treatment, the highest number of harvested fruits was obtained in the P₀ treatment (4.06 fruits) significantly different from P₁, P₂, and P₃ which were 1.09, 0.56 and 0.69 fruits, respectively. In the drought stress treatment, the highest number of harvested fruits was obtained in the C₀ treatment (2.00 fruits) and was not significantly different from C₂ and C₃ which had values of 1.50 fruits and 1.63 fruits respectively but significantly different from C₁ presented in Table 2.

3.9. Fruit diameter (mm)

The largest fruit diameter in paclobutrazol treatment was obtained in P₀ (13.49 mm) and significantly different from other treatments. The smallest fruit diameter was given to P₂ (5.01 mm). In the drought stress treatment, the largest fruit diameter was obtained in the C₀ treatment which was 10.87 mm, significantly different from the other treatments presented in Table 3.

Table 2 Effect of paclobutrazol treatment and drought stress on time to flowering (DAT), number of flowers formed (florets), number of fruits formed (fruits) and number of fruits harvested (fruits)

Treatment	Flowering start time (DAT)			Number of flower formed (florest)			Number of fruit formed (fruit)			Number of fruit harvested (fruit)		
Concentration of paclobutrazol (ppm)												
P ₀	17.44	(3,40)	a	8.00	(3.00)	a	6.00	(2.25)	a	4.06	(1.83)	a
P ₁	20.14	(3,61)	a	5.00	(2.00)	c	4.00	(1.76)	d	1.09	(1.08)	a
P ₂	7.50	(2,49)	b	6.00	(2.00)	bc	4.00	(1.96)	c	0.56	(0.96)	a
P ₃	17.44	(3,36)	a	7.00	(2.00)	ab	5.00	(2.04)	bc	0.69	(0.99)	a
LSD 5%	0.51			1.00			0.13			1.38		
Drought stress (%)												
C ₀	14.00	(3.07)	a	7.00	(2.00)	a	6.00	(2.16)	a	2.00	(1.31)	a
C ₁	14.13	(3.07)	a	6.00	(2.00)	a	4.00	(1.91)	b	1.19	(1.08)	a
C ₂	16.14	(3.31)	a	6.00	(2.00)	a	4.00	(1.77)	c	1.50	(1.22)	a
C ₃	18.25	(3.41)	a	6.00	(2.00)	a	6.00	(2.16)	a	1.63	(1.25)	a
LSD 5%	0.51			1.00			0.13			1.38		

Description: Numbers followed by the same letter in the same treatment and column show no significant difference in the 5% level of the least significant difference test (LSD). The numbers in parentheses are the result of data transformation. While the numbers that are not in parentheses are the original data.

3.10. Total fruit weight (g)

The highest total fruit weight in paclobutrazol treatment was obtained in P₀ (18.68) significantly different from all treatments P₁ (2.78 g), P₂ (2.00 g) and P₃ (2.50 g). The lowest fruit weight was given by P₂ and significantly different from P₀, P₁ and P₃. In relation, P₀ treatment gave higher weight than P₂ by 89.29%. In the drought stress treatment, the highest fruit weight was obtained in C₀ which was 9.98 g and significantly different from C₁ and C₂ and C₃ respectively (4.66 g), (6.34 g) and (4.97 g) presented in Table 3.

3.11. Total soluble solids (PTT) (°Brix)

In paclobutrazol treatment, the highest total soluble solid was obtained in P₀ (5.71 oBrix), significantly different from other treatments. The lowest total soluble solid was given to the treatment P₃ (1.26 Brix) which was not significantly different from P₂, but significantly different from P₁. In relation to total soluble solids P₀ was higher than P₃ by 77.93%. In the drought stress treatment, the highest total soluble solid was given to C₀ (3.97 oBrix) and significantly different from C₁ and C₂ respectively 2.76 oBrix and 2.51 oBrix but not significantly different from C₃ presented in Table 3.

3.12. Average weight per fruit (g)

In the paclobutrazol treatment, the highest average weight per fruit was obtained in P₀ (3.27g), significantly different from P₁ (1.68). P₁ treatment was significantly different from P₂ and P₃ which were 1.19 g and 0.91 g respectively but P₂ and P₃ were not significantly different. In this case, the average weight per fruit in P₀ was higher by 72.87% than P₃ Percentage of fruit set (%) presented in Table 3.

In the drought stress treatment, the average weight per fruit in C₀ (2.26 g) was higher than the treatments C₁ (1.15 g), C₂ (2.13 g), C₃ (1.51 g) which were not significantly different in all treatments. In this case the average weight per fruit in C₁ is smaller than C₀ by 49.37% presented in Table 3.

Table 3 Effect of paclobutrazol treatment and drought stress on fruit diameter, total fruit weight, soluble solids and average weight per fruit

Treatment	Fruit diameter (mm)			Total fruit weight (g)			Soluble solids (°Brix)			Average weight per fruit (g)		
Concentration of paclobutrazol (ppm)												
P ₀	13.49	(3.25)	a	18.68	(3.53)	a	5.71	(1.95)	a	3.27	(1.73)	a
P ₁	6.66	(2.07)	b	2.78	(1.48)	bc	3.49	(1.45)	b	1.68	(1.27)	b
P ₂	5.01	(1.72)	d	1.00	(1.28)	d	1.67	(1.10)	cd	1.19	(1.11)	c
P ₃	5.57	(1.76)	cd	2.50	(1.29)	cd	1.26	(1.04)	d	0.91	(1.03)	c
LSD 5%	0.32			0.31			0.29			0.13		
Drought stress (%)												
C ₀	10.87	(2.79)	a	9.98	(2.24)	a	3.97	(1.59)	a	2.66	(1.44)	a
C ₁	4.53	(1.59)	c	4.66	(1.56)	c	2.76	(1.36)	a	1.15	(1.09)	c
C ₂	8.01	(2.30)	ab	6.34	(1.99)	ab	2.51	(1.27)	b	2.13	(1.39)	a
C ₃	7.31	(2.12)	bc	4.97	(1.80)	b	2.90	(1.32)	ab	1.51	(1.23)	b
LSD 5%	0.32			0.31			0.29			0.13		

Description: Numbers followed by the same letter in the same treatment and column show no significant difference in the 5% level of the least significant difference test (LSD). The numbers in parentheses are the result of data transformation. While the numbers that are not in parentheses are the original data.

Table 4 Effect of paclobutrazol treatment and drought stress on fruit set percentage (%), fruit drop percentage (%) and oven dry weight (g)

Treatment	Fruit set percentage (%)			Percentage of fruit fall (%)			Oven dry weight (g)		
Concentration of paclobutrazol (ppm)									
P ₀	0.15	(2.93)	ab	28.56	(4.39)	C	12.39	(3.12)	a
P ₁	0.19	(3.17)	a	53.92	(6.08)	B	8.99	(2.68)	b
P ₂	0.11	(2.27)	b	63.69	(6.92)	A	8.70	(2.63)	cd
P ₃	0.18	(3.24)	a	61.40	(6.54)	Ab	8.71	(2.63)	d
LSD 5%	0.66			0.64			0.13		
Drought stress (%)									
C ₀	0.13	(2.70)	c	53.21	(6.19)	Ab	8.94	(2.66)	b
C ₁	0.17	(2.92)	bc	59.05	(6.51)	A	9.91	(2.79)	a
C ₂	0.25	(3.80)	a	44.82	(5.37)	C	9.73	(2.78)	a
C ₃	0.09	(2.18)	d	48.19	(5.85)	Bc	10.21	(2.83)	a
LSD 5%	0.66			0.64			0.13		

Description: Numbers followed by the same letter in the same treatment and column show no significant difference in the 5% level of the least significant difference test (BNT). The numbers in parentheses are the result of data transformation. While the numbers that are not in parentheses are the original data.

3.13. Percentage of fruit set (%)

In paclobutrazol treatment, the highest percentage of fruit set was in P₁ (19.44%), which was not significantly different from P₀ and P₃, which were 14.56% and 18.40%, respectively. The lowest percentage of fruit set was obtained in P₂ (10.75%) and significantly different in all treatments. In the drought stress treatment, the highest percentage of fruit set was obtained in C₂ which was 24.55% significantly different from C₀ (13.06%), C₁ (16.33%) and C₃ (8.72%). The lowest percentage of fruit set obtained in C₃ is presented in Table 4.

3.14. Percentage of fruit drop (%)

The highest percentage of fallen fruit in paclobutrazol treatment was obtained in P₂ (63.69%) which was not significantly different from P₃ but significantly different from P₀ and P₁ which were 28.56% and 53.92% respectively. The lowest percentage of fallen fruit was obtained in P₀. In the drought stress treatment, the highest percentage of fallen fruit was obtained in C₁, 59.05%, which was not significantly different from P₀, but significantly different from C₂ and C₃, 44.82% and 50.49% respectively. The lowest percentage of fallen fruit was obtained in C₂ (44.82%) and significantly different from C₀, C₁ and C₃ presented in Table 4.

3.15. Root oven dry weight (g)

In paclobutrazol treatment, the highest root oven dry weight was obtained at P₀ (12.39 g), significantly different from other treatments. The lowest oven dry weight was given to P₂ (8.70 g) which was not significantly different from P₁ and P₃ levels. In the drought stress treatment, the highest oven dry weight was obtained in C₃ which was 10.21 g and was not significantly different from C₁ and C₂ but significantly different from C₀ (8.94 g) presented in Table 4.

4. Discussion

Total weight of harvested fruit per plant was highest in the treatment without paclobutrazol P₀ (18.68 g). The high total weight of harvested fruit in the P₀ treatment was supported by the variable of fruit formed which was proven by the correlation value of fruit formed to the total weight of harvested fruit with a real positive correlation ($r = 0.5640^*$). The number of flowers formed is also one of the variables that support high total fruit weight as evidenced by the correlation value of flowers formed to the total weight of harvested fruit with a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.7517^*$) and shows that P₀ tends to produce more flowers. This is supported by the results of research [8] in the results of his research the use of 300 ppm paclobutrazol decreased the number of fruits and fruit weight in tomato plants, as well as research conducted [9] paclobutrazol treatment did not increase the number of flowers on chili plants. The decrease that occurred was thought to be due to the concentration of paclobutrazol which was too high, thus disrupting the metabolic process in the plant. This is also supported by the variable percentage of fallen fruit in the P₀ treatment which is smaller (28.56%) compared to the P₂ paclobutrazol treatment (63.69%). Flowering time in this study the use of paclobutrazol P₂ 20,000 ppm accelerated the beginning of flowers compared to other treatments. This study is in line with [5] that paclobutrazol treatment can accelerate the time of the first flower appearance on mangosteen.

The lowest harvest fruit weight was obtained in the treatment of paclobutrazol concentration of 20,000 ppm P₂ (2.00 g) which in this case the application of paclobutrazol reduced the harvest fruit weight per plant by 89.29%. The treatment of paclobutrazol caused the total weight of harvested fruit to decrease. It was thought to be due to the high concentration of paclobutrazol that caused the process of fruit development to be inhibited. The results showed that the use of paclobutrazol made the number of fruits less than without paclobutrazol. Similar results were reported by [10] that the weight of harvested fruit with treatment without paclobutrazol was higher than with paclobutrazol treatment in tomato plants.

The high number of fruits and the number of flowers formed is influenced by plant growth. Evidently the number of fruits formed is supported by a positive correlation in plant height to the number of fruits formed ($r = 0.3647$) and a real positive correlation to the number of flowers formed ($r = 0.6083^*$). The real positive correlation value shows that the higher the value of plant height, the more flowers formed. This is in line with research [9] that the application of paclobutrazol inhibits the height of potted chrysanthemum flower plants.

As a result of the high concentration of paclobutrazol, fruit enlargement is disrupted so that in the treatment of paclobutrazol, the diameter of the fruit tends to be smaller than without paclobutrazol. The average value of weight per fruit is one of the important variables that affect the harvest weight because the higher the average value of weight per fruit, the value of total fruit weight will increase as evidenced by the real positive correlation value on the average weight per fruit to the total fruit weight (0.5894^*). High harvest fruit weight is also supported by the variable number of harvest fruits as evidenced by a real positive correlation to harvest fruit weight ($r = 0.9314^*$). High total fruit weight was supported by rapid flowering time as evidenced by a positive correlation value ($r = 0.2952$) to total fruit weight and was also supported by fruit set percentage as evidenced by a positive correlation value to total fruit weight ($r = 0.0381$).

Chlorophyll content, leaf relative water content and root oven dry weight in the paclobutrazol treatment were higher than the treatment without paclobutrazol. These three variables did not support the total weight of harvested fruits as indicated by the correlation value of chlorophyll content, leaf relative water content and oven dry weight to total fruit weight with a negative correlation ($r = -0.3972$). Low chlorophyll content causes the photosynthesis process to run slowly and affects the growth of fruit weight. According to [11], the chlorophyll content of each chloroplast increased in

beet plants treated with paclobutrazol. In this treatment, the chlorophyll content in P₂ (36.88 SPAD) was higher than P₀ (35.62 SPAD). This study is in accordance with [12] that paclobutrazol treatment increases chlorophyll content in siamese orange plants.

Drought stress treatment at C₀ control showed the total weight of harvested fruit (9.98 g) and fruit diameter (10.87 mm) higher than the total weight of harvested fruit at 80% stress level C₁ (4.66) and fruit diameter C₁ (4.53 mm). This is supported by 6 other variables, namely plant height (8.07 cm), number of flowers formed (7.00 florets), number of fruits formed (5.69 fruits), number of harvested fruits (2.00 fruits), average weight per fruit (2.26 g) and total soluble solids (3.97 °Brix) which have high values compared to the 80% water stress level. These results are in line with research [13] that normal water levels (100%) showed a higher number of flowers, number of fruits and fruit diameter. This is evidenced by the positive correlation to fruit weight. However, root length in P₃ drought stress treatment at 60% of field capacity showed higher root length compared to normal water application. Root length was not correlated to the number of flowers formed, number of fruits formed, number of fruits harvested, number of fruits dropped, total fruit weight and soluble solids. Meanwhile, [14] reported that drought stress did not significantly increase root length.

The high number of fruits formed will increase the total weight of harvested fruits, this is supported by the average weight per fruit significantly positively correlated with the total weight of harvested fruits ($r = 0.5894^*$). This is supported by the relative water content (RWC) of the leaves which is characterized by a positive correlation value of RWC leaves to the average weight per fruit ($r = 0.1675$). The low leaf chlorophyll in drought stress treatment caused the plant to produce not optimal, characterized by a negative correlation value of leaf chlorophyll to the number of flowers formed ($r = -0.2171$), percentage of fruit set ($r = -0.1652$), number of fruits harvested ($r = -0.3704$), weight per fruit ($r = -0.4794^*$) and total fruit weight ($r = -0.3972$). The percentage of fallen fruit has a direct influence on the total weight of harvested fruit and weight per fruit as evidenced by the significant negative correlation values of ($r = -0.7431^*$) and ($r = -0.4345^*$) respectively. The correlation values illustrate that the higher the percentage of fallen fruit, the lower the total harvest weight and weight per fruit.

5. Conclusion

Paclobutrazol treatment increased fruit set, chlorophyll content, leaf relative water content, root length, accelerated flower emergence time, decreased number of fruits formed, number of harvested fruits, fruit diameter, weight per fruit, root oven dry weight, total soluble solids, and harvested fruit weight. Drought stress treatment increased leaf relative water content, root length, root oven dry weight, percentage of fruit set and decreased leaf chlorophyll content, percentage of fallen fruit, number of flowers formed, number of harvested fruits, fruit diameter, weight per fruit, total soluble solids, harvested fruit weight and slowed down flowering time. The interaction between paclobutrazol treatment and drought stress had no significant effect on all observation variables.

Suggestion

Further research needs to be done on the use of paclobutrazol on strawberry plants with lower concentrations because the lowest concentration of 10,000 ppm still greatly suppresses strawberry growth. In addition, to determine the field capacity, do preliminary experiments more than once.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

References

- [1] Horticulture statistics province of Bali 2021 [Internet]. 51000.2230. 2022 [cited 2022 Nov 26]. p. 17. Available from: <https://bali.bps.go.id/publication>. [Indonesian]
- [2] George AP, Nissen RJ. Effects of water stress, nitrogen and paclobutrazol on flowering, yield and fruit quality of the low-chill peach cultivar, Flordaprince. *Sci Hortic (Amsterdam)*. 1992, 49(3–4):197–209.
- [3] Asín L, Alegre S, Montserrat R. Effect of paclobutrazol, prohexadione-Ca, deficit irrigation, summer pruning and root pruning on shoot growth, yield, and return bloom, in a “Blanquilla” pear orchard. *Sci Hortic (Amsterdam)*. 2007, 113(2):142–8.

- [4] Khurshid T, McNeil D., Trought MC., Hill G. The response of young ‘ Braeburn ’ and ‘ Oregon Spur Delicious ’ apple trees growing under an ultra-high density planting system to soil-applied paclobutrazol: I . Effect on reproductive and vegetative growth. *Sci Hort* (Amsterdam). 1997, 72:11–24.
- [5] Rai IN, Poerwanto R, Darusman LK, Purwoko BS. Regulation of Off-season Flowering of Mangosteen (*Garcinia Mangostana* L.) Plants by Strangulation, and Application of Paklobutrazol and Etepon. *Bul Agron*. 2004, 32(2):12–20. [Indonesian]
- [6] Rahayu RS, Poerwanto R, Efendi D, Widodo WD. Appropriate Duration of Drought Stress for Madura Tangerine Flower Induction. *J Hortik Indones*. 2020, 11(2):82–90. [Indonesian]
- [7] Roosa V, Karyawati AS, Armita D. The Effect of Ground Water Level and Magnesium Sulfate ($MgSO_4$) Fertilization to Growth of Strawberry Plant (*Fragaria x ananassa* Duch .). *J of Crop Prod*. 2019, 7(8):1401–9. [Indonesian]
- [8] Syaputra E, Nurbaiti, Yoseva S. Effect of Paklobutrazol on Growth and Production of Tomato (*Lycopersicum esculentum* Mill.) with Pruning of One Main Branch. *JOM FAPERTA* [Internet]. 2017, 4(1):1–11. Available from: <https://jom.unri.ac.id>. [Indonesian]
- [9] Adilah R, Rochmatino R, Prayoga L. Effect Of Paklobutrazol And Ga_3 on Growth and Flowering In Chili Plants (*Capsicum annum* L.). *BioEksakta J Ilm Biol Unsoed*. 2020, 2(1):109. [Indonesian]
- [10] Moko R, Sompotan S, Supit PC. Paclobutrazol Application on Growth and Production in Tomato Crops (*Lycopersicum esculentum* Mill.). 2018, 1–8. Available from: <https://ejournal.unsrat.ac.id/v3/index.php/cocos/article/download/22086/21787/0>. [Indonesian]
- [11] Dalziel J, Lawrence DK. Biochemical and biological effects of kaurene oxidase inhibitors, such as paclobutrazol. *Monogr Plant Growth Regul Gr*. 1984,
- [12] Rumada Iw, Rai In, Dwiyani R. Out-of-Season Fertilization of Siamese Orange (*Citrus microcarpa* L.) with Flowering Induction Treatment and Dormancy Breaking Agent. *Agrotrop J Agric Sci* [Internet]. 2021 May 31, 11(1):10. Available from: <https://ojs.unud.ac.id/index.php/agrotrop/article/view/73593>. [Indonesian]
- [13] Yunus A. Correlations and Path Analysis of Some Characters in Chili Pepper (*Capsicum annum* L .) Under Normal and Drought Stress). *J Hort*. 2019, 29(2):147–58. [Indonesian]
- [14] Tang D, Wei F, Qin S, Khan A, Haneef M. Industrial Crops & Products Polyethylene glycol induced drought stress strongly in fl uences seed germination , root morphology and cytoplasm of di ff erent kenaf genotypes. *Ind Crop Prod* [Internet]. 2019, 137(January):180–6. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2019.01.019>